

MATERIALS FOR TEACHING ENGLISH: LITERATURE, NEWSPAPERS, TV, RADIO, INTERNET

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Abstract: This article aims at analyzing the importance of using Mass Media in the classroom and finding the ways how to use Printed and Audio-visual Media. It is the result of an in-depth study, surveys and questionnaires thus trying to make the ideas in this article more trustworthy. It is based not only on the literature review but also on long personal experience. It is a brief description of some practical examples and some tips for novice teachers. Further more, this article tends to deal with some of the key issues of using media in the classroom. Here are included some of the findings of my research work on a post-doctorate Fulbright Program in 2001. The following issues are open for discussion: the importance of Media in general and in education in particular; Media are persuasive and pervasive, newspapers, magazines, radio, television and internet in the classroom, etc.

Keywords: teaching English, multimedia in education, mass-media in education.

Introduction

Using various kinds of Media in the classroom has always been a challenge, and how to bring these Media in the classroom is more than a challenge. Students and teachers should be able to use in their classrooms different media through different technologies. Media provide teachers and students with creative and practical ideas. They enable teachers to meet various needs and interests of their students. They also provide students with a lot of language practice through activities using newspapers, magazines, radio, TV, movies, books, Internet, etc, and tasks which develop reading, writing, speaking and listening skills. They entertain students and encourage reading English in general, both inside and outside the classroom, promoting extensive reading by giving the students the confidence, the motivation and the ability to continue their reading outside the classroom. Media “inform, amuse, startle, anger, entertain, thrill, but very seldom leave anyone untouched”. (Shirley Biagy, 1996) Bearing in mind all these features and positive input of Media in Education I thought to undertake this study to give my modest contribution to the enhancement of teaching and learning English. I undertook a lot of surveys, questionnaires and interviews to make this issue more persuasive and more practical for the students. Based on my experience and the study in this field I also aimed at giving some practical

advice and tips how to use Media in the classroom. As classroom teachers it is necessary to bring mass media in our classrooms exactly for all these reasons mentioned above. We should understand the media, the messages they give and their influence upon us, how to explore this abundant information and create a continuum of the liveliness media create in the life of people and why not in the classrooms where students spend a lot of their time.

It has been almost ten years that the following questions have always been in my mind:

1. How can Media help my students speak more?
2. How can classroom Media presentations help my students speak freely?
3. How can I help my students not to forget what they learn through Media?
4. How can we exploit a piece of learning material offered by various Media?

Through my research work on a post-doctorate Fulbright Program and my long experience with student teachers I have found some answers to the above questions but I am sure there are many other ways, hundreds to maximize the effectiveness of Media in the classroom.

Here are some findings and answers to the questions:

Media provide huge information, they motivate students to speak and help them integrate listening, reading, talking and writing skills, through various kinds of activities.

A clear example are Power Point presentations which help students speak freely, eye contact, organize ideas. Through Media Presentations there is more communication and collaboration among students, while working with the pages of a book is more individual, less collaborative and less interactive. There is so much information available at the click of a mouse but at the same time you have the feeling that there is little memory space in the brain and students may forget everything, so, try to select the most important things and review and review till they are located in the long-term memory.

We can exploit a piece of learning materials offered by various Media in several different ways through: analyzing a text in the book, reading and generating ideas from a text in the newspaper or magazine, watching and discussing a TV program or a movie, classroom presentations, exercises and activities using various kinds of Media, pair and group work, reconstructing the text based on the above information brought from different Media,

engaging students in useful writing and revision activities, etc.

Once we mention the phrase “Multimedia in Education” it comes to our mind technology, computer, Internet, etc.

On one hand we are right because nowadays the phrase “Technology in Education” has become the ‘buzz’ word in every educational environment. We the university teachers should think how to help student teachers to use Media successfully in their future career, especially think of what is practically hidden behind them.

On the other hand, “Multimedia in Education” does not only mean computer and internet. We should not forget the use of other media, as each of them gets priority every now and then while being used in the classroom.

“We live in a world where media are omnipresent. An increasing number of people spend a great deal of time watching television, reading newspapers and magazines, playing records and listening to the radio... The school and the family share the responsibility of preparing the young person living in a world of powerful images, words and sounds” (UNESCO Declaration on Media, 1982)

Why are the Media Important? Media are important because we get to know the world through using them; we understand the world and try to change it. Media Education is important because it develops students’ creative powers for those images, words and sounds that come to the students from various Media. Thus, creating more active and critical media users, who will always be more demanding in the future.

Media Education has to do with film and television, press and radio, their impact on the students’ progress. It has to do with *what* to teach through media, *when* and *how*. Its aim is to enable students to develop critical thinking, analyzing and reflecting on their experiences while using various means of Media.

Media Influence is Pervasive and Persuasive. Media today have an enormous impact. They have become so important that it is rarely that we can live without them. Every morning we may wake up with the radio music in the background, or we play a tape while having shower or being dressed. Someone may run to the PC or laptop to check the mail or the news. On the way to school or work we may grab a newspaper and have a look at the headlines. At school we may go to the library and consult a lot of books and magazines for our research project. At home we may watch television for a while, etc, etc. Each of these experiences puts us in contact with a medium, or channel of communication. Radio, books, records and tapes, newspapers, magazines, movies, television, on-line media, new media, all these are called *mass media*, they reach many people at one time.

In the years to come, media will become more pervasive. Understanding

them and their influence will be crucial to wise use.

So, as said above, everyday, everyone is affected by the Mass Media in some way or another, when you study a textbook for school, when you turn on the radio in your car, when you see a movie on TV, etc. The collective effects on society of all these media choices are tremendous; some times we are not aware of.

Despite the criticism of the mass media, most thoughtful persons agree that mass media do a superior job in reporting the news and informing the public. It's our task as teachers to help students and pupils understand this information, transmit it to the coming generations and try to use it for education purposes.

Mass media provide students with a lot of language practice through activities using newspapers, magazines, radio, TV, movies, books, Internet, etc, and tasks which develop reading, writing, speaking and listening skills. They also provide students with lots of inside and outside classroom activities, promoting extensive reading by giving the students the confidence and the ability to continue their reading outside the classroom and above all they enhance motivation. Media keep us informed about what is happening in the world, they extend our knowledge and deepen our understanding.

Nowadays the information is abundant, it comes through different sources, but we should try how to benefit from this information, how to learn about specific issues, how to become aware of problems, opportunities and resources, how to find issues we are interested in, how to identify the issues that have impact on us, etc. So, it is easy to get this information but it is difficult to choose and more difficult to bring it to the classroom.

Newspapers and the classroom

Newspapers are easy to be brought in the class in different subjects and courses, especially in geography, history, literature, language classes, etc. Some of them have valuable information for these subjects, but we should know how to find this information. Many libraries have systems of classification according to the topics and issues and we can easily find our way in searching this information. If not we would spend a lot of time to find something. It is often said that academic success starts at the library.

There are different purposes and ways for using newspapers in language classroom. They may be used for the *culture* they transmit. The more widely students read, the greater their understanding of this cultural meaning will be. They may also be used for reflecting *changes in the language* as well, and in doing so, helping students and teachers keep up pace with such changes.

Most newspapers are linguistically up-to-date and provide valuable linguistic data. They may be used for the wide variety of *text types* and *language styles*, not often found in textbooks. At the same time, newspapers provide a natural source of many of the *varieties* of Written English that become very important to students, and valuable for language study as the students progress. So, they may be used as supplementary material and examples in Text Analysis, Academic Writing, Stylistics, Semantics, etc. while analyzing different types of texts.

“People learn through reading, and reading about interesting new things in one’s interest subject, undoubtedly helps motivation”. (Paul Sanderson, 2002)

The *variety* of subjects and topics makes newspapers interesting and motivating for the students to work with. Newspapers report real-life events, and this arouses students’ curiosity. Newspaper-based activities in the classroom may engage students in enjoyable activities and encourage their further reading. Newspapers are an invaluable source of *authentic materials*. The more students read, the more they want to explore.

Newspapers are also a great source for *ESP teachers*. They can be used as teaching materials to develop students’ language skills. They can be used effectively with a wide range of levels from Elementary to Advanced, either interpreting them or using them as they are. Some newspapers are easy to read, easy to use. The committed teachers can design exercises to develop reading comprehension, critical thinking skills, writing skills, grammar skills, vocabulary, map/chart reading skills, geography skills, social study skills and more. Having a lot of newspapers and information the teachers should be careful with the way how to organize a certain activity using them. So, they are particularly suitable *for mixed-ability classes*, depending on the activity, questions, etc. In planning a lesson using a newspaper, the teacher should take into consideration the length of the article, paragraph, the complexity of the language, the density of information, the subject-matter and content, the time available and the level of the students.

Nowadays, we are living in a period of rapid technological changes in mass communications. Through Internet, we are now able to access thousands of newspapers and magazines worldwide. Internet has increasingly become a major source of newspapers and magazines for language teachers; just find the web site and click. But we should be very careful in choosing suitable newspaper materials to use with our students.

It is helpful to bear in mind these questions: (Paul Sanderson, 2002).

Will my students find the materials interesting? If yes, they will raise students' motivation. If no, the students will be frustrated.

Are the materials appropriate for their level of knowledge? If they are too difficult to be understood, students will be discouraged. Otherwise their level of understanding would be O.K.

Are the materials appropriate for the students in terms of language level? Choose more challenging materials, choose materials where the language level is suited to the level of students, choose tasks that can be done by the students at a certain level.

Should I use only materials from today's newspapers? The answer is yes and no.

Lessons take time to prepare. The schedules of the teachers are periodically busy. Once we find an interesting material, we may use it over and over again, avoiding articles or news mentioning dates or topical events, data for well-known personalities, etc.

Another very important issue about newspaper use is *materials collection*. It is an on-going process and worth doing it. Choosing and collecting short articles, weather forecast, advertisements, headlines, etc. is a hard task, but we may use them at a later time and more than once for different students. So, it is necessary to be very careful in organizing newspaper materials. Once we start collecting them we should begin thinking to organize them, put under certain categories, systematize them, etc. Everyone has experienced many times the frustration when he/she knows that he/she has that piece of information but does not remember where he/she has put it. It is good to categorize the materials under certain titles, headlines, advertisements, etc. or under topic titles, sport, cinema, relationship, according to language level of students, etc. Of great importance are the use of the *photographs* and *illustrations*. We should be careful to prepare these materials in good quality to use them again and again, and with every passing year we create folios and enrich them, then photocopy what we want for students' use.

We should not avoid using newspapers in the classroom only thinking that they are *difficult* for our students. It is true that the language there is difficult, but after all it is authentic. There are several ways of making newspaper materials usable for the various levels of students, by selecting interesting newspapers and the students will be interested in reading them and would skip some difficult expressions. A very important thing that enhances success in using newspapers in the classroom is the careful design of *tasks*. "Grade the task – not the material" is a well-known maxim in

language teaching'. (Paul Sanderson, 2002) In spite of the difficulty of the texts, the task should suit the level of students, this is more important than the difficulty of the text.

Magazines in the Classroom

There are different kinds of magazines. According to a questionnaire done with high school and university students most of them mentioned that they liked to read mostly political, scientific, fashion, cultural, entertaining and sport magazines. This interest of the university and high school students should be exploited by the teachers to up-date their teaching materials and break the monotony of the lesson by using always the textbooks.

As with newspapers, magazines are resources for different subjects, cutting out pictures and passages associated with particular topics. Magazines are also sources in language development in providing pictures to stimulate verbal or written stories. For example, they may be used for introducing colors and clothes, means of transport, short stories, stimulating picture discussions and for other supplementary materials as well, which cover a topic that may be under discussion in a language class.

As for the ways how to use magazines in the classroom we can refer to the ideas and clues given for the newspapers. Both newspapers and magazines have a lot of things in common.

The Role of Books in Everyday Life and Education

'Those who have already discovered the joy of books, however, are hooked for life. And as others become aware of the vast array of books available, they too will find that unrivaled knowledge and pleasure await them between the covers of books' (Beckert, 1992).

Books are crucial in modern life as well, a driving force in education, business, law, science, medicine and entertainment. Through books the students gain the legacy of knowledge earned by those who came before. (Beckert, 1992) People of all ages find information, pleasure, relaxation and inspiration while reading books. Books lack the immediacy of other mass media, but they make up for that by greater thoroughness and permanence. Books are saved and treasured in great public libraries and in personal collections. Readers go back to famous books, rereading them again and again. Others enjoy a book once and pass it on, wanting others to share their discoveries.

There is also a vast area that *textbooks* cover. Besides them there are a lot of books that we read as a class assignment, a novel in the English class, in the course English through Prose and Poetry, in British and American literature course; a book on the planets in the science class, and many others.

So, books are among the most enduring of the mass media. Some people save them for years, and libraries save them for centuries. Here is the right place to mention the words of Franklin Roosevelt: "People die, books never die".

Radio and Education

Radio plays an important part in developing people's imagination, in creating pictures in the mind through the power of words, it stimulates the imagination to fill in the visuals, etc. The listeners see the drama in their heads. Thus, when radio is used in the classroom it helps students to promote their imagination, to voice their creativity.

A lot of radio programs contribute to language learning. Besides getting new information and entertainment, in language classes radio helps the pronunciation, the intonation, the pitch of voice, etc. These might be successful if we undertake adequate preparation and design carefully graded tasks. Students gain a feeling of satisfaction from having understood something of an authentic broadcast, we can see the joy in their faces. They develop greater confidence in their ability to cope with English as it's spoken outside the classroom. Albanian students may use BBC World Service news bulletin, Voice of America or other foreign radio stations. In case students have no possibilities, the teacher may record the news bulletin, transcribe it and prepare to explain any difficult vocabulary that may come out. Then the teacher may ask the students if they have listened to the news in Albanian the day before, because nearly all the news, especially international news, is almost the same. So if the content is somewhat known to the students, they will be more motivated and the success of the task will be easier.

In the classroom the students may be put into groups to discuss what is going on in the world and what they predict they are going to listen to. The teacher or one of the students may write all the predictions on the blackboard.

The first step might be to listen to the headlines, several times, as they are short, but convey a lot. Then the teacher may ask the students to identify which of the stories they predicted are included in the headlines.

Then ask the students various questions about, what has happened? Where did it happen? How many different stories have you heard for the same event? etc. Then let the students listen to the news bulletin 2-3 times and then give them time to discuss about the above questions. In the meantime the teacher may explain any key vocabulary.

We know that it is difficult, but if we can make copies of the news bulletin, it would be possible to organize follow-up activities. Students may transcribe certain stories, use dictionaries to check the meaning of unknown words,

group words according to various fields, etc. They may also compare the language of the news bulletin with the language of a newspaper of the same date and the same topic. So, we can organize listening and reading comprehension activities.

At last the students may report on what they have listened to. There might be tens of different activities using radio in the classroom. We have practiced these procedures with such topics as: The War in Iraq, Pollution and Environment, Global Warming, Weather Report, Poverty, Holidays, etc.

Television and the Classroom

Most people today watch about three to five hours of television a day. 'Defenders call TV a window on the world, a magic carpet of discovery. They claim that it enlarges both knowledge and understanding. Defenders say it encourages a new way of thinking, with interlocking hopes, needs and problems. Critics call it the idiot box. They say it promotes mindless viewing of mindless programs. Critics say it stifles creativity and promotes distorted thinking. Social observers often urge parents not to use television as an electronic baby-sitter'. (Beckert, 1992)

Documentaries are also educational. Documentaries on Wildlife, on Civil War, on Discovery Channel, and others, have opened valuable windows for our students. Through them our students can learn about languages, cultures, science, etc. Some of these documentaries, if carefully selected may be used successfully in the classrooms and be a part of the curriculum. They may help students to better understand the subject.

As we can not use TV information when it is given, we can bring this information into the classroom through videotaping various TV programs for later use. Often activities using television, video and movies overlap, there is not a strict division among them.

Using Movies to Teach English

We should encourage the students to see as many films as possible outside the classroom or parts of films in the classroom. Watching films is very important as it increases their visual and critical awareness. Watching films in the classroom can be realized through recording them. We have tried to make the activity of film-watching an active rather than a passive one. This can be done in a variety ways as setting questions about the film, promoting discussions in small groups, asking the students to comment on various things, inviting criticism, etc. We may also stop the film from time to time and ask the students what has happened so far or guess what might happen next. Another way might be turning the sound down and asking the students

to imagine or make up dialogues.

"The eye is more powerful than the ear". (Jane Sherman, 2003)

Anyway it is difficult to use films in the classroom. Sometimes they are difficult to understand but Western Films for example are easy to understand because there is a lot of action in them. Some other films are easy to understand because there is a clear conventional story line, as love stories, epics and science-fiction drama which have simple plots. Of great importance are the subtitles and dubbing which might be in English. They help a lot the aim of helping learning English through films, depending on the procedure the teachers decide to follow. Sometimes the teachers recommend students to see a film dubbed into or subtitled in Albanian, if possible, before seeing it in English. It would be great to find English films with English subtitles. They make understanding the language easier as listening to authentic language is more difficult than seeing the expressions written, thus matching the words with pictures and voice. Jane Sherman says,

In this case the students are offered both reading and listening. Judging from our experience usually students prefer more reading than listening, with few exceptions.

While using a film in the classroom to help our English we have paid attention to the accent, voice, body language, choosing of the words, training ear and the eye, lifestyle, plot idea, summary, what's going on, why and how, and many other things depending on the aim we have put to ourselves. The overall aim has always been to maximize comprehension and learn more English. But we all know that watching a full feature film needs more time than teaching hours. So, we need to be able to fit films into a classroom schedule organizing different activities that help this aim. In order to save time we might tell the story of the film ourselves, illustrating it by showing three or four key scenes without telling the end. Another way is the use of video-cassette. The students may watch the film themselves in the video-classroom or at home and come the next day and present what they watched and what happened in the film.

Another way of using the films to teach English is that of comparing the film with the book if the same story appears in both ways. This kind of activity can be done before or after watching the film, it can be used to adopt or compare characters, to compare differences and similarities, using the Venn Diagram, between the book and the film, the examples might be numerous. The book may be used to supplement and clarify the film, but at

the same time the film may be used to illuminate the book. All these could be done through several activities.

We may also give assignments to our students, write about your favorite film, your favorite characters, your favorite actors, what makes them your 'favorites', the differences you see if a book has been made into a film, etc. When a preliminary work is done before watching the film the above activities may produce interesting writing activities. These kinds of activities also contribute to the promotion of critical thinking especially in evaluating films and improving language skills.

Other ways of using films in the classroom are: Segmenting the film, pre-watching, while-watching and post-watching activities, which are very useful as cloze exercises, quizzes, related readings, web sites, film presentations, discussions, research work, etc.

The role of the teacher in the Technology era

Today the role of the teacher has changed a lot. Traditionally a teacher's job has been "to fill" the minds of students with "true" knowledge. The teacher was the only authority that gave information. Students were supposed to give their knowledge back to the teacher through retelling and reporting. But today the teachers should be aware of their new role and responsibilities that high technology requires from them.

Today students are supposed to conceptualize ideas, work as part of a collaborative team, problem solve, and take action. In today's world, the teacher must go beyond knowledge transmission.

The change of the role of the teacher is conditional by the development and implementation of new technology in the classroom. Once the computers are found the classroom environment should be changed. This brings another dimension to the role of the teacher, that of a facilitator and a manager.

The classroom becomes a multidimensional environment. It is difficult for the teachers to manage this multidimensional environment. It is essential for them to make the students able to use the computer and at the same time deal with other activities such as researching for information from books and magazines, collecting data from observations, gathering information from a videotape, or conducting an experiment, etc. etc. This type of environment is student-centered, very active and requires careful planning and cooperation from the students. The students should be able not only to use computers but also manage the extra resources required by technology as well.

Time has come that Internet be considered as a tool to promote learning.

The success of this tool will depend upon students' and teachers' ability not only to examine and make sense of information they encounter, but also to evaluate this information.

We all know that nowadays teacher is no more the only source of information. Among other roles, the teacher today is a kind of a 'conductor' of the orchestra, where musicians (students) are different and play (learn) differently (Lawrence Tomei, 2002). Media being multi-dimensional realize this mission successfully and differently.

Conclusions

Multimedia helps us teachers make teaching and learning visual (easy for visual learners). A picture not only tells a thousand words but it also helps students improve their thinking and observation skills, it promotes imagination, etc. Playing the video with or without the subtitles enhances visual learners. Radio (playing the audio) helps auditory learners learn better. Listening to the tape and then having the script is a clear combination that helps visual and auditory learners.

By using various kinds of Media in the classroom we can enhance students' understanding and promote it where necessary.

The use of audio and video with student teachers is crucial also in giving feedback and training, in Reflective Teaching, in analyzing and synthesizing, in tracking students' progress over time, in editing certain options, in testing, in peer coaching, etc.

Media can help with many issues such as: motivation, clarity, recycling, drafting, revising, editing, variety, mixed-ability classes, updating information in the textbook, giving life and color to classroom procedures and methods, thus at the same time helping the students improve accuracy and fluency. There are a lot of issues that can or cannot be solved by media.

Internet has three main educational uses. It serves as a source of information, a place for collaboration, and a place to learn and publish.

Some years ago it was thought that the computers would substitute the teachers but it did not work. Learning and teaching through computers is an alternative approach that stresses the student's use of computers to solve real-world problems while learning. But however sophisticated it might be, teachers will never be replaced.

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